

“A STUDY MOTIVATION PROCESS IN SHREE DUTTA FOUNDERS AND ENGINEERS”**Mrs. Madhuri P. Rasal**

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Abstract: -

Foundry industry plays very important role in the development of Kolhapur district. Foundry industry means where the metal casting is produced. Foundry is factory that produces metal casting. Metals are cast into shapes by melting them into liquid, pouring the metal in a mould and removing the mould. In all foundries human resource management is very important. P. Jain 1st 2013. Motivation is one of the important processes followed by leaders in all foundries. Motivation is important factor that, affecting human behavior and performance in foundry industry. For the success of foundry manager gives lots of importance to motivation process. According to Likaert motivation is a core of management. Shri dutta founders and engineers PVT Ltd, Kolhapur It is located in plot no B-MIDC. Shirol, kolhapur-416122. Ph.(0230) 2468316,460034, E Mail datta-f@bsnl.in. This foundry is established in the field of production of gray cast iron and S.G. Casting. It is one of the successful industries in MIDC. There are 130 employees working in this foundry. It has covered area about 2250 sq. mtrs and its total build up area is about 1000 sq. mtrs. The total area covered by the manufactured purpose is about 750 sq mtrs. In this foundry management plays all its important function. In this research researcher is going to focus on motivation process.

Keywords: Motivation, foundry, employees, management, needs, behavior.**Introduction**

Motivation is a concept which includes the terms like motives, needs, wants, drives, desires, wishes, incentives etc. motive is an inner state that energizes, activates and directs behavior of employees towards goals. Rao P. N. 2013. There is difference in need and want. Needs includes desires both physiological and psychological. Wants include only those desires for which a person has money and also desire to spend money to satisfy the wants. Motivating is a process in which one person stimulates another person to engage in action, ensuring to satisfy the motives in a direction that is satisfying to both the organization and the employees. Motivation is the channelization and activation of motives, motivation is the work behavior itself. Motivation depends on motives and motivating process. According to McFarland “Motivation refer to the way in which urges drives, desires, aspirations, strivings, or needs direct, control, or explain the behavior of human beings”.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study the motivating process in Dutta Foundry.
2. To study the motivation Techniques in Shree Dutta Foundry.

3. To give the impact of motivation Techniques.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

This paper helps to understand the motivation process in Shree Dutta Founders and Engineers. This motivation process helps for the attainment of higher level of productivity, to create better image of foundry in society, to make employees more capable and to eliminate the negative attitude of employees.

RESEARCH DATA AND METHODOLOGY

The proposed study mainly is descriptive in nature. It is mainly based on primary and the secondary sources. Primary data and information is collected from the discussion and interviews with authorized person and secondary data is collected from the relevant books, documents of various departments, articles, research papers and web-sites are used in this study.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The study is covered only five years period ie from 2014 to 2018. The study is mainly focused on the motivation function of management in Shri Dutta Founders and Engineers.

CHARACTERISTICS OF MOTIVATION

1. BASED ON MOTIVES

Motivation is based on individual's motives. These motives are in the form of feelings that the individual lacks something. In order to overcome this feeling of lackness employees tries to behave in a manner which will helps in overcoming this feeling. Sinha Nirmal 2005.

2. AFFECTED BY MOTIVATING

Motivation is affected by way the individual in motivated. The act of motivating channelizes the need satisfaction. It can also activate the needs which are less strong and harness them in a manner that would be functional for the organization.

3. GOAL-DIRECTED BEHAVIOR

Motivation leads to goal-directed behavior. A goal directed behavior is one which satisfied the causes for which behavior takes place. Motivation has influence on human behavior.

4. RELATED TO SATISFACTION

Motivation is related to satisfaction, satisfaction means the contentment experiences of an individual which he drives out of need fulfillment. Thus, satisfaction is a consequence of rewards and punishments associated with past experiences. It provides more satisfaction.

5. PERSON MOTIVATED IN TOTALITY

A person is motivated in totality and not in part. Each; individual in the foundry industry is self constrain unit and his needs are interrelated. These affect his behavior in different ways moreover, feeling of needs and their satisfaction is a continuous process. These create continuity in behavior.

6. COMPLEX PROCESS

Motivation is a complex process. Complexity emerges because of the nature of needs and the type of behavior that is attempted to satisfy those needs. Thus, complexity is generated in motivation process.

TECHNIQUES OF MOTIVATION

Khanzode V.V. 1992, Motivation techniques help the managers in applying motivation process. These techniques help for the better performance. There are number of techniques and programmes that have accepted in practice by Shree Dutta Foundry. Some of these techniques are as follows.

1. Management by Objectives

People can set goal for themselves and then put in efforts to achieve the objectives of foundry industry.

2. Job satisfaction

It is a positive feeling or attitude that individuals have towards their jobs and works. Employees are highly satisfied with job means he really likes his job, feel good about it and he values his job highly.

3. job enrichment

A job is enrichment by making it more exciting, challenging and creative or gives at the job holder more decision making, planning and controlling powers for better performance.1

4. Job enlargement

It means adding few more task element horizontally. Foundry make job enlarge by involving performing variety of jobs or operations.

5. Job rotation

When an activity is no longer challenging the employee could be rotated to another job, at the same level, with the same skill requirement. It gives the same effect as the job enlargement.

6. Business promotion

The technique can create positive feedback both from inside and outside the workplace. Foundry industry give employee small things like helmet, safety boot, medical facility, coffee as success depends on employee satisfaction.

7. Survey

Survey can provide good feedback of any topic. Foundry can use this feedback to solve the problems and to find out the solutions this method is also useful for progressive decisions.

8. Building employee re organization programme

Foundry designed these programmes mainly to motivate employee through awards and incentives. By giving awards and rewards it is possible to motivate employees for work hard and to achieve objectives for foundry industry.

9. Understanding employee

According to this techniques employee not just observe the work, but try to find out what they like to do outside of work. Thus employee will come to know how much do care about objectives.

10. Enjoyable work environment

This technique helps in motivating employees to increase their performance level. Sometimes fun is also a great way to manage the stress and boredom.

11. Assemble roundtable committee

This techniques help to bring together five or six key people like middle department heads. Their group representative and group leaders will ask to give their opinion and if they have any suggestions. This technique make employee to feel important person in foundry organization structure.

12. Positive reinforcements

This motivation technique is used daily. In past leaders have used fear tactics or negative motivations, which creates only negative atmosphere. But in modern days, it become needs of foundry industry to appreciate employees.

13. Build trust and respect

Building trust and showing respect is hard enough in life. In foundry work place is very hard without trust and respect. Motivation will not be existed if there is no respect for each other among employees.

14. Job training

The most common purpose to give job training for employee in foundry industry is to give their employee latest knowledge about their job. These motivation techniques make employee more perfect by increasing their skills and talents. On the job training and off the job training are given to employees in foundry industry for their betterment and success. Chandan J. S. 1996.01

IMPACT OF MOTIVATION

* ATTAINMENT OF HIGHER LEVEL OF PRODUCTIVITY:

A good motivation process help to increase the physical and mental capabilities of employees, to reduce the cost of operations, better utilization of resources is most important, motivation help up to do this. Motivation process is goal oriented process so it always helps to do profitable operations. Greater the motivation process, greater will be the chance for attaining the higher level of success. Mamoria C. B. 1984.

* PROJECTIONS OF THE BETTER IMAGES

The foundry which always provide new opportunist for the financial and personnel advancement always create a better image in the employment market. Such foundry can easily attract qualified employees for

business development. It means good motivation process simplifies the staffing function in foundry industry.

*** CORDIAL HUMAN RELATIONS**

A motivational process provides a job satisfaction. Job satisfaction will result in cordial relationships between employer and employees and thereby reduces industrial disputes, employees turnover and absenteeism. Motivation process help to increase employee morale and discipline and they will become more loyal and dedicated to foundry industry.

*** ELIMINATION OF EMPLOYEE'S NEGATIVE ATTITUDE**

Satisfied employees are quickly motivated to work hard for the foundry objectives with great cooperative performance. Employee will become more adaptive to any change introduced by the management. This way effective motivation process always helps to overcome the negative attitude of employees. Motivation is a best remedy for the restrictions and strikes etc.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

Table No.1.1

Table showing classification of employees according to the level of education

Level of education	No of Respondent	Percentage
Illiterate	20	15
Up to SSC	50	39
Up to HSC	30	24
Up to Graduation	20	15
Engineer	10	07
Total	130	130

The above table shows the e category of employees who are more educated, less educated and who are illiterate. This can be made clear by using following diagram

Graph No. 1.1

From the above table it is clear that 15% are graduate and 7% are engineer who have educated the technical knowledge.

Table1.2

Table showing opinion of Employees about Motivation Process

Opinion	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Excellent	70	54%
Good	30	23%
Satisfactory	30	23%
Unsatisfactory	00	00%
Total	130	100%

Source: Field Survey

Table shows that above 54% employees are having the opinion of excellent method of motivation process in shri Dutta Founders and Engineers and there is no unsatisfactory opinion about it.

Graph No. 1.2

Table No 1.3

Table showing awareness of Employees about Motivation Techniques

Opinion about Motivation Techniques	No of respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	110	77%
No	20	23%
Total	130	100%

It has been found that from survey, about 77% employees are aware about the motivation techniques followed by Shri Dutta Founders and Engineers. This is helpful to make the industry more successful.

Graph No. 1.3

Table No 1.4**Table showing opinion about Performance improved after Motivation Process**

Opinion about performance	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Yes	120	92%
No	10	08%
Total	130	100%

From the above table it is clear that 92% of employees from selected respondent think that there working speed and performance has been improved and increase to good level of success because of motivation process in Shree Dutta Foundry.

Graph no 1.4

CONCLUSIONS

Motivation is the process of challenging employee's inner drives so that he wants to accomplish the goals in the foundry industry. Motivation is a behavior concept by which we try to understand why people behave as they do. So it has been concluded that motivation is one of the most important factors affecting human behavior and performance. So manager has to give more importance to motivation process in foundry industry. Motivation is a core of management. A motive is an inner state that energizes, activates or moves and that directs the behavior of employees towards goals. Needs and wants are different needs are more comprehensive and include desires both physiological and psychological and wants are narrow

and include only those desires for which a person has money and also the desire to spend money to satisfy the wants.

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